

Economics and politics

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Annotation: : The relationship between politics and economics, how politics can affect the economy, and can they be distinguished from each other or not? The answers to these questions are presented in detail in the article.

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The ECONOMY is any activity of people related to the provision of material living conditions.

POLITICS is the activity of state power in the field of governance and international relations; the activity of a particular social group, party, class, determined by their goals and interests.

The relationship between politics and economics is of a direct nature. The economy plays a decisive role in this relationship. It forms the material basis of politics. The development of economic processes determines policy. The content of politics, certain political decisions and actions are ultimately determined by the economic interests of people. Genuine politics is nothing but the conscious use of economic laws. This shows one side of the relationship between politics and economics. However, their relationship is not one-sided.

How politics can affect the economy?

When the subjects of production processes begin to conflict, then the intervention of politics in these economic relations by nature becomes necessary.

It should be noted that the political system is still more independent in decision-making compared to the economic one. But there is one caveat — the political course largely depends on domestic economic relations. Although external political pressure (for example, international sanctions) leads to changes in the structure and principles of the economy in the country.

Why do governments interfere?

The Government may decide to regulate certain aspects of economic activity in order to stimulate economic growth or prevent negative economic conditions in the

future. In general, the active role of the Government in responding to and influencing the economic conditions of the country is aimed at preserving and promoting the economic interests of the general public.

Is it possible to separate politics and economics from each other?

A key aspect of anarchism is the idea that the political and economic aspects of society cannot be separated. This means that economic freedom is inseparable from political freedom and vice versa. If representatives of the working class submit to authoritarian political organizations, then their economic freedom will also be limited, and, conversely, if their economic freedoms are limited, then their political freedoms will also be limited. As Proudhon put it, "industrial freedom is inseparable from political freedom."

Politics is determined by various factors, including economic ones, and also directly depends on the social structure of society, the level of social stratification. On the other hand, politics is able to influence these areas, to penetrate them. **This is due to two aspects of politics:**

a) although the policy is not really aimed at creating material and spiritual values (they are created in other spheres), but the policy is designed to provide conditions under which the creation and appropriation of values would meet the interests of certain social groups. This feature of politics is reflected in the widely presented definitions of power as an instrument for the distribution of values in society.;

b) politics is present in all public spheres by virtue of its inherent regulatory function. Such types of state policy as economic, military, scientific and technical, social, cultural, environmental, etc., are aimed at improving relations between people in these areas, as well as at a more rational use of social values.

What innovations are being made today in the policy of Uzbekistan for the development of the economy?

The Central Bank has approved two scenarios for the development of the economy of Uzbekistan for 2023-2025. Their development took into account the continuing high uncertainty in the world, the decline in prices for basic goods, limited opportunities for financing from the budget, the need for reforms and much more.

The Central Bank of Uzbekistan has approved the main directions of monetary policy for 2023 and the period 2024-2025 (pdf).

Since the end of 2021 and the first months of 2022, economic recovery has been observed in most countries of the world. However, since the end of February, there has been high inflationary pressure caused by the crisis situation between Russia and

Ukraine and fluctuations in the energy market, a delay in bringing supply volumes in line with high demand, as well as a retaliatory tightening of monetary policy, the review says.

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